

Highlights

To hedge or not to hedge? Cryptocurrencies, gold and oil against stock market risk

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- Hedging strategies using cryptocurrencies, gold and oil against stock market risk are considered
- We determine in what market conditions these instruments reduce stock market risk more effectively
- We demonstrate that neither strategy can beat dynamic or naïve hedging with futures contracts
- Investors have no motivations to implement cryptocurrencies, gold or oil in hedging strategy against stock market risk

To hedge or not to hedge? Cryptocurrencies, gold and oil against stock market risk^{*,**}

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ABSTRACT

The article aims to determine whether any hedging strategy against stock market risk, performed using instruments popular in the literature (gold, cryptocurrencies and oil), can beat index futures. As a hedging strategy, we understand a pair-wise portfolio consisting of a long position in stocks (base investment) and a short position in a hedging instrument put together to minimise the portfolio variance. As a benchmark, we analyse optimal and naïve hedging strategies with futures contracts. We demonstrate that, regardless of the stock market, the best hedging strategy focused on variance minimisation requires using index futures. Both strategies: the optimisation-based one and the naïve one, beat the dynamic strategies utilising the remaining hedging assets. Therefore, from the risk-minimisation point of view, investors have no motivation to implement cryptocurrencies, gold or oil in hedging strategy against stock market risk.

1. Introduction

An inherent element of investing in stock markets is price risk. Aside from potential return on investment, risk is the most crucial characteristic to consider when buying stocks. Many investment practitioners believe that increasing volatility and volatility spikes effectively discourage participation in the equity markets and encourage investment in less-volatile asset classes (Washer, Jorgensen and Johnson, 2016). They are inclined to hedge their trading portfolios to reduce risk exposure and avoid potential losses during periods of uncertainty or to direct their attention to safer investments. The Global Financial Crisis, the Eurozone Sovereign Debt Crisis, the COVID-19 pandemic and Russia's invasion of Ukraine are the most important events that have intensified discussion on hedging strategies.

In literature, one can distinguish two main definitions of a hedge. According to the first one, popularized by Baur and Lucey (2010) together with the concepts of safe-haven and diversifier – a hedge is a security that does not co-move with the base asset on average. If its returns increase when the underlying asset falls below some extreme, pre-specified quantile, it is called a (strong) safe-haven. An instrument can be a weak safe-haven if it does not lose value when the base asset experiences extreme declines. Eventually, a diversifier is, on average, positively correlated with the base asset (Baur and Lucey, 2010). In this case, the hedging strategy implies including the base asset and the potential hedge in the portfolio, with pre-specified weights that can be modified during the investment period. Hedging properties in this approach are examined with the help of regression or quantile-regression tests, e.g. Baur and Lucey (2010); Owusu-Junior, Adam and Tweneboah (2020). Some authors apply threshold-based or causality tests, while others investigate dynamic correlation (Akhtaruzzaman, Boubaker, Lucey and Sensoy, 2021; Będowska-Sójka and Kliber, 2021) or relationships in tails (Echaust and Just, 2022). Regarding instruments used as potential hedges, three assets in literature prevail: gold, oil and cryptocurrencies. Historically, gold was used as a default hedge asset, while cryptocurrencies as the new gold, dominate the newest literature.

The second approach focuses on a classic hedging strategy, which involves taking an opposite trading position in the hedging instrument to a related asset or portfolio to offset its losses. Such hedging is the subject of this work. It can involve a variety of strategies, but traditionally, investors perform it with options, futures, and other derivatives.

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The problem of choosing preferred hedge instruments was explored in non empirical and empirical studies. The first strand of the literature involves the expected utility framework and finds the rationale for using linear and nonlinear instruments for hedging purposes. Battermann, Braulke, Broll and Schimmelpfennig (2000) analysed the optimal choice of hedging instruments of a firm exposed to market risk (exchange rate) when either futures or options are available. In the presence of unbiased futures and options prices, they showed that futures' hedge effectiveness is greater than options for each concave utility function. With futures contracts, maximal hedging effectiveness occurs at a full (perfect) hedge strategy. Holthausen (1979) found that the optimal hedging strategy depends highly on the risk manager's expectation due to the future price of a risky asset. If the forward price is less than the expected future price, the risk manager generally hedges some, but not all, risky exposure in the forward market. The manager will hedge more the more risk-averse he or she is and will hedge more as the riskiness of the uncertain price increases. Moschini and Lapan (1995) analysed hedging decisions of the risk manager facing both futures and options markets within an expected utility model that allows for basis risk. When futures and options prices are unbiased, optimal hedging requires only futures, and options are redundant in optimal hedging. Options may be used in optimal hedging strategies when market prices are perceived as biased. Bias risk accompanies investors when the correlation between risky exposure and hedging instrument is not perfect. It means that only arrangements made over the counter (i.e. forward contract) can hedge investment against market risk perfectly. Otherwise, the problem of the choice of hedge instruments is an open case.

Within this classical approach, over the past years, a growing number of empirical studies also focused on other hedging instruments against stock market risk, most commonly gold, cryptocurrencies and oil. The following section describes the main results obtained for these instruments applied in the hedging role. The main objective of this paper is to verify the hedging ability of gold, three cryptocurrencies: Bitcoin, Ether and Tether and crude oil to serve as hedging instruments against stock market risk versus the simple strategy based on futures contracts. We address the following research questions.

- What is the effectiveness of hedging strategies using gold, cryptocurrencies or crude oil compared to hedging with index futures contracts?
- Since the hedging effectiveness is time-varying, when are these instruments more effective in stock market risk reduction?
- : Given the widespread availability of futures contracts, do these instruments (gold, cryptos and oil) deserve so much attention in the hedging role?

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first empirical research which compares hedging effectiveness based on traditional futures contracts with widely explored new candidates for hedging instruments. This study is also the first to summarise the results for hedging effectiveness of gold, cryptocurrencies and oil presented in other studies. Hence, our contribution to the literature is mainly to verify the rationale of using gold, cryptocurrencies or crude oil to hedge stock portfolios in the minimum variance approach.

The optimal hedge ratio is a function of both the risk-return possibility curve that is available in the market and the investor's utility function (Cecchetti, Cumby and Figlewski, 1988). In this paper, we do not consider the profits of the hedged portfolio. To provide comparable results on hedging effectiveness to recent literature, we also assume that an investor is interested in minimisation of the entire risk of the portfolio in a one-day hedging horizon. The literature review and computations based on the Kroner and Sultan (1993) hedge ratio indicate the low effectiveness of these instruments as hedges. We demonstrate that index futures contracts outperform them, regardless of whether futures are applied in the optimal or naïve hedging strategy. Therefore, from a risk-minimisation point of view, investors have no reason to implement cryptocurrencies, gold or oil in hedging strategies against stock market risk.

2. Literature review

A constantly growing body of instruments is considered a potential hedge in literature. The review below concentrates on the three most frequently tested assets: gold, oil and cryptocurrencies. From the variety of approaches scholars utilise, we focus on the classic hedging strategy that assumes that an investor holds a long position in the base asset or portfolio and minimises the portfolio variance by holding a short position in a potential hedge.

2.1. Hedging effectiveness of gold against stocks

Relatively low volatility of gold makes it a good candidate for a potential hedge. However, the hedging property of this precious metal can vary from market to market and over time, but is relatively low.

For instance, Akhtaruzzaman et al. (2021) examine hedging property of gold relative to stock markets (S&P 500, Euro Stoxx 50, Nikkei 225, and China FTSE A50 indices) in different phases of the COVID-19 pandemic. Using the dynamic conditional correlation (DCC) model for high-frequency data, their results show better hedging effectiveness of gold during phase I (December 31, 2019–March 16, 2020) of the pandemic. In phase II (March 17, 2020–April 24, 2020), after interventions of governments with monetary and fiscal stimulus packages, gold lost its hedging property. Hedging effectiveness (HE) measure decreased on average from 22.41% for S&P 500 and 11.46% for Nikkei 225 in the first phase to 2.59% and 3.63%, respectively in the second phase. However, for two other indices hedging effectiveness was very low even in the first phase of pandemic (3.25% and 4.68%, respectively).

Chemkha, BenSaïda, Ghorbel and Tayachi (2021) use the asymmetric dynamic conditional correlation to find the dynamic relationship between S&P 500, Euro Stoxx 50, Nikkei 225, FTSE 100 and gold and compare the hedging effectiveness in the pre-COVID-19 and in the COVID-19 pandemic. Although during the COVID-19 pandemic hedging effectiveness of gold is higher than in the pre-COVID-19 period with the exception for the FTSE 100, gold is able to reduce only 2.92%, 3.67% and 2.97% of returns variance of S&P 500, Euro Stoxx 50, Nikkei 225, respectively. In the case of FTSE 100 higher HE is obtained for the pre-COVID-19 period (2.54%).

Dong, Li and Yoon (2021) investigate the hedging effectiveness of gold for small open economies including Korea, Taiwan, Hong Kong and Singapore stock markets from January 4, 2000 to March 31, 2020. They adopted the trivariate dynamic conditional correlation-fractionally integrated asymmetric power ARCH model and unconditional quantile regression model. The findings show that classic hedging strategy performs the worst among considered strategies including optimal portfolio weight strategy (long position in gold) and equal weighted portfolio. The hedging effectiveness of the strategy is the highest for Korea and equals to 1.9% under regular situations and 2.4% under extreme situations.

Shahzad, Bouri, Roubaud and Kristoufek (2020) compare gold and Bitcoin hedging potential for the G7 stock markets from July 10, 2010 to December 31, 2018. Based on the DCC model they find that gold produces higher hedging effectiveness than Bitcoin for each of the G7 countries (except for Canada) and for the MSCI G7 index. However, results for HE prove poor ability of both assets to serve as a hedge for stock markets. The highest HE is obtained for the CAC 40 index and it equals to 6.2% with gold as a hedge. Bitcoin is not able to reduce any portion of risk of considered stock markets.

Ma, Sun, Zhai and Jin (2021) compare the effectiveness of bonds with gold hedging the stock market risk. The authors analyse three periods of uncertainty: the Global Financial Crisis (July 2007–March 2009), the US debt ceiling crisis (August–October, 2011) and the US-China trade war (March 2018–December 2019). The effectiveness of gold as a hedge was low, reaching its maximum of 1.75% in the third period.

Salisu, Vo and Lucey (2021) examine the hedging relationship between gold and US sectoral before and during-COVID-19 pandemic. Optimal hedge ratio differs across sectors for both sample periods considered, supporting the arguments that different sectors behave differently to the gold hedging. Based on estimated hedge ratios instead of HE the authors show that the hedging effectiveness of gold for stocks declined (in absolute term) during the COVID-19 period across all the sectors considered relative to those obtained for the pre-COVID-19 sample.

Generally, gold due to its low correlation with stock markets performs well as a hedging instrument in a long position (Baur and McDermott, 2010; Beckmann, Berger and Czudaj, 2015; Boubaker, Cunado, Gil-Alana and Gupta, 2020) however, can no longer be an effective hedging instrument in the classic hedging strategy.

2.2. Hedging effectiveness of oil against stocks

Since many authors document spillovers between the oil and equity markets differing in magnitude, depending on the market segment, time period (crisis versus tranquil) and nature of the shocks (Aroui, Jouini and Nguyen, 2012; Zhang, 2017; Kliber and Łęć, 2022), it was natural that oil has become another popular instrument considered as a possible hedge against the risk, of equities or indices. The effectiveness of such a hedge varies depending on the oil index (Brent versus WTI), the equities or indices hedged and the time of the study.

Lin, Zhou, Jiang and Ou (2021) investigate risk spillovers and hedge strategies between global crude oil markets and stock markets. The authors use weekly prices of the international stock index (Chinese Shanghai stock index, S&P 500 index and Stoxx European 600 index) and weekly prices of the global crude oil market (WTI, Brent, and Dubai).

Using dynamic hedge ratios, the authors obtained time-varying hedging efficiency up to 6% for the US index and WTI and up to 3% for the European stocks and Brent.

Batten, Kinatader, Szilagyi and Wagner (2021) study economic benefits from hedging stocks (MSCI portfolios) with oil in the long time span 1990–2017. They show that the optimal hedge ratio is not constant over time. Hedging effectiveness does not exceed 10% on average although there are periods of good oil performance. *HE* increases rapidly in 2008 and maintains high level until 2012. Oil is able to reduce even 54% of the portion of MSCI North America variance in June 2012 and 52% of MSCI G7. Another conclusion from the research is that Brent oil is better suited for equity-oil hedging than WTI. The latter contains a local price spread due to the logistics of oil movements at the Cushing, Oklahoma oil storage and distribution hub.

Antonakakis, Cunado, Filis, Gabauer and de Gracia (2020) examine the optimal hedging strategies and optimal portfolio weights for implied volatility portfolios between oil and fourteen asset volatilities. The instruments analysed in the paper belong to four different asset classes: stocks, commodities, exchange rates, and macroeconomic conditions. According to the results presented in the paper, the oil price implied volatility index (OVX) is highly correlated with the US and emerging stock market volatility indices. One observes the lowest correlation between OVX and the implied volatilities of gold and the Euro/dollar exchange rate. Comparing the cost of the OVX hedge, the authors conclude that OVX could be particularly useful to hedge long positions in the CBOE Energy Sector ETF volatility index, Euro/dollar currency volatility index, China ETF volatility index, and Gold ETF volatility index. However, the authors document maximal hedging effectiveness only for the strategies when the implied volatility indices provide a hedge against the OVX. The effectiveness of such an optimal-weights strategy reached 32.5% for the NASDAQ-100 volatility index and of the optimal hedge strategy reached 68.4% for CBOE Equity VIX on the Goldman Sachs volatility index.

We notice that hedging effectiveness of oil does not differ much from the hedging effectiveness of other commodities. Chunchachinda, de Boyrie and Pavlova (2019) document the average effectiveness of hedging equity markets with iShares S&P GSCI Commodity-Indexed Trust ranging from 6% for MSCI Frontier 100 to 15.9% for MSCI Emerging Markets. However, the effectiveness of oil as a hedge can be improved if we use intraday data. Kuang (2022) studies the effectiveness of equity-oil hedge using high-frequency data. The scholar analyses the Brent crude oil and four equity indices; S&P 500, Dow Jones 30 (DJ30), FTSE 100, and DAX 30. To overcome the problem of non-synchronous trading, the author uses the contracts for the difference (CFD) on Brent and equities published by the Dukascopy Swiss Banking Group. The sample period in the study spans from October 1, 2013, to April 23, 2021. The study documents variance reduction up to 24% using intraday data.

2.3. Hedging effectiveness of cryptocurrencies against stocks

Together with the growth of popularity of cryptocurrencies, researchers are starting to explore their potential as a safe-haven, hedge or diversifier. The potential stems from the fact that the cryptocurrencies are independent from central authorities. The obvious obstacle is their high volatility, which – according to some researchers – disqualifies them from being one of such assets (Baur, Hoang and Hossain, 2022).

The most popular cryptocurrency analysed in the context of hedging is Bitcoin. Pal and Mitra (2019) compare hedging effectiveness of Bitcoin against S&P 500 for a variety of GARCH specifications. The authors assess the effectiveness of the hedge out-of-sample, for different frequency of data and different forecast length. The maximal effectiveness of the hedge does not exceed 5%. Similar small values of the effectiveness have been obtained by Naeem, Hasan, Arif and Shahzad (2020) for the period spanning between May 1, 2013, and June 28, 2019 and for 10 industry portfolios composed from various stocks.

Chemkha et al. (2021) report the results for developed markets. During the COVID-19 pandemic hedging effectiveness of Bitcoin relative to S&P 500, Euro Stoxx 50, Nikkei 225 and FTSE 100 is much higher than before and equals to 12.49%, 17.99%, 4.91%, and 5.70%, respectively. They conclude that cryptocurrencies are still extremely risky assets and using them in hedging strategy may lead the portfolio to excessive volatility.

More and more authors explore the potential of other cryptocurrencies to hedge the portfolio composed of stocks. For instance, Yousfi, Zaied and Tliche (2022) document that Ethereum has better effectiveness as a hedge against S&P 500 than Bitcoin. Ustaoglu (2022) investigate the hedging properties of Bitcoin and Ether relative to 27 emerging stock market indices before and during the pandemic period using the asymmetric dynamic conditional correlation. The highest hedge effectiveness of the optimal weights-based strategy during the pre-COVID-19 pandemic period is 27.4% for the Argentina–Bitcoin portfolio and 14% for the Argentina–Ether portfolio. The *HE* decreased substantially during the COVID-19 period compared to the pre-COVID-19 period for most stock markets.

Table 1
Descriptive statistics of returns.

	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Median	Max	Range	Skewness	Kurtosis
CAC 40	0.0034	1.6965	-13.8459	0.0511	8.6701	22.5161	-0.6311	8.8091
DAX	-0.0004	1.7381	-13.8024	0.0681	11.0283	24.8308	-0.3614	9.0670
FTSE 100	-0.0137	1.5722	-13.4738	0.0777	10.4600	23.9338	-0.9052	11.3986
S&P 500	0.0218	1.6118	-12.7652	0.0881	8.9683	21.7335	-0.7454	10.9437
Nikkei 225	-0.0100	1.4480	-9.3603	-0.0057	7.7494	17.1096	-0.0705	4.2348
Hang Seng	-0.0499	1.6420	-6.5737	-0.0318	8.8078	15.3815	0.3158	3.0307
F.CAC 40	0.0035	1.7088	-13.9659	0.0398	8.8510	22.8170	-0.6457	8.8033
F.DAX	0.0002	1.7271	-12.5007	0.0831	10.6786	23.1792	-0.3042	7.0273
F.FTSE 100	-0.0124	1.6036	-12.0443	0.0601	10.0808	22.1251	-0.8046	8.9089
F.S&P 500	0.0225	1.5928	-10.9552	0.0823	9.3446	20.2998	-0.8044	10.3134
F.Nikkei 225	-0.0099	1.5034	-12.0258	-0.0335	7.4903	19.5161	-0.5425	6.6090
F.Hang Seng	-0.0492	1.7102	-6.9999	-0.0680	9.5293	16.5293	0.2360	3.3086
BTC	0.0760	3.8824	-46.4730	0.0835	17.1821	63.6551	-1.6388	20.5387
ETH	0.2022	5.1659	-55.0732	0.2909	23.0695	78.1427	-1.3598	14.4885
USDT	0.0000	0.3274	-5.2570	0.0001	5.3393	10.5963	0.4559	135.3060
F.Brent	0.0335	3.2791	-27.9761	0.3138	19.0774	47.0536	-1.5201	16.3734
F.Gold	0.0234	1.1064	-5.1069	0.0563	5.7775	10.8844	-0.2546	3.9347

Jiang, Lie, Wang and Mu (2021) analyse relationships at different quantiles and frequencies employing a quantile coherency approach to report the hedging potential of six cryptocurrencies for six stock market indices in 2015–2020. Ether is reported to be the most effective hedge with the *HE* of 18%–24% for the MSCI markets, developed markets and S&P 500.

Eventually, stablecoins are analysed as potential hedges, but mostly within the hedge definition of Baur and Lucey (2010). For instance, Vukovic, Maiti, Grubisic, Grigorieva and Frömmel (2021) and Kliber (2022) show that stablecoins could have been used as safe-haven against American stocks during COVID-19 pandemic, Gadi and Sicilia (2022) – that stablecoins Tether (USDT) and USD Coin (USDC) are the most effective hedge/havens compared to other cryptocurrencies against stock market indices of the G7 and BRICS markets, and Yousaf and Yarovaya (2022) – that investors can reduce the risk of Islamic sectorial equity portfolios by adding the Islamic gold-backed cryptocurrencies (Onegram and X8X). Therefore, we decided to analyse the effectiveness of shorting stablecoins against stocks as well.

3. Data

In this study, we investigate and compare the hedging role of gold, crude oil, cryptocurrencies, and stock market index futures for stock markets. We use the prices of COMEX Gold Futures (F.Gold), ICE Europe Brent Crude Futures (F.Brent), Bitcoin (BTC), Ether (ETH), Tether (USDT), and the individual stock market indices of six countries (France – CAC 40, Germany – DAX, the United Kingdom – FTSE 100, the United States – S&P 500, Japan – Nikkei 225, and Hong Kong – Hang Seng) as well as the individual stock index futures (Euronext Paris CAC 40 Futures – F.CAC 40, Eurex DAX Futures – F.DAX, ICE Europe FTSE 100 – F.FTSE 100, CME E-Mini S&P 500 Futures – F. S&P 500, Osaka Exchange Nikkei 225 Futures – F.Nikkei 225, and HKFE Hang Seng Futures – F.Hang Seng). We extract the daily data from the Refinitiv Eikon database, except for the cryptocurrency price series, which we obtain from the service finance.yahoo.com. The prices of all assets are expressed in US dollars to eliminate the influence of exchange rate movements. The data covers periods of turbulence in the global financial markets during the COVID-19 pandemic and the Russia–Ukraine war, i.e. the sample period spans from January 2nd, 2020, to December 30th, 2022. We included only those observations for each asset pair that occurred in both time series.

Table 1 presents summary statistics for the log-returns of assets. Brent, gold and two cryptocurrencies, namely Bitcoin and Ether, have higher mean returns than stock indices. However, Brent, Bitcoin and Ether suffer from high volatility in returns (measured by standard deviation and range), while gold has lower volatility than stock indices. Among the hedge candidates, Tether shows the lowest volatility and has the least extreme movements in price. This result is unsurprising because Tether is a stablecoin whose tokens are backed by an equivalent amount of US dollars.

The kurtosis values are positive for all assets, indicating a leptokurtic distribution. In turn, skewness is negative (except for Hang Seng Index, Hang Seng Futures, and Tether), suggesting a fatter left tail of the distribution.

4. Methods

4.1. Hedging ratio

In our paper, we concentrate on a risk-minimizing hedge. One of the simplest ways to hedge risk using futures is the so-called *naïve hedge*. In that case, the investors with a long position in a base instrument sell a unit of futures today and repurchase it at the end of the investment when they sell the base instrument. If the prices of both instruments move by the same amount, the investors' net positions will be unchanged, and the hedge will be perfect.

However, the prices of the base and hedge instruments do not always move by the same amount. Therefore, the following model has been proposed:

$$S_t - S_{t-1} = \alpha + \beta(F_t - F_{t-1}) + \varepsilon_t, \quad (1)$$

where S_t denotes the price of the base instrument at time t , F_t – the price of the futures contract at time t , and ε_t is the idiosyncratic component. Thus, an investor who wants to minimize the portfolio's risk should sell β USD of the futures contract for each one-dollar worth of the base asset. This strategy is called *conventional hedging*. Ederington (1979) shows that the value of β is equal to:

$$\beta_{OLS} = \frac{h_{sf}}{h_f}, \quad (2)$$

where h_{sf} denotes the covariance between the base asset and the hedge, and h_f – the variance of the hedge. In this approach, the hedge ratio is calculated as the least-squares estimator of the regression (1). The drawback of this approach is that it assumes a constant joint distribution for changes in both variables, which is violated especially during periods of high market volatility. Moreover, this static hedging strategy fails to consider the time-varying adjustments needed in the overall hedging strategy (Miffre, 2004; Shrydeh, Shahateet, Mohammad and Sumadi, 2019). Therefore, it is advisable to use the dynamic approach proposed by Kroner and Sultan (1993), where the h_{sf} and h_f are replaced by the conditional covariance and variance, respectively.

Thus, the hedge ratio becomes:

$$\beta_t = \frac{h_{sf,t}}{h_{f,t}}, \quad (3)$$

where $h_{f,t}$ is modelled with the help of GARCH-type models, and $h_{fs,t}$ – using multivariate GARCH with static or dynamic conditional correlation.

Further, the assessment of the performance of the hedging portfolio is done based on hedging effectiveness ratio, HE , defined as:

$$HE_t = \frac{var_{unhedged,t} - var_{hedged,t}}{var_{unhedged,t}} \quad (4)$$

where $var_{unhedged}$ denotes the variance of returns of the unhedged portfolio, which consists of one instrument – the base one, while var_{hedged} is the variance of a portfolio, which consists of both base instrument and the hedge. Variance of such a portfolio is calculated as follows:

$$var_{hedged,t} = h_{s,t} - 2\beta_t \cdot h_{sf,t} + \beta_t^2 h_{f,t}. \quad (5)$$

The values of the hedging effectiveness index range from 0 to 1. The former denotes no hedge, and the latter the perfect one.

4.2. Univariate GARCH models

Let us denote by y_t a vector of time series, and by Ω_{t-1} – the set of information available up to the moment $(t - 1)$. Let us denote the conditional mean of y_t as:

$$y_t = E(y_t | \Omega_{t-1}) + \epsilon_t, \quad (6)$$

where $E(\cdot | \cdot)$ is the conditional expectation operator, and ϵ_t – the disturbance term with $E(\epsilon_t) = 0$, $E(\epsilon_t, \epsilon_s) = 0, \forall t \neq s$. In the case of daily financial time-series, conditional mean is typically modelled with one of AR, MA or ARMA models, while the ϵ_t can be decomposed in the following way:

$$\epsilon_t = z_t h_t^{1/2}, \quad (7)$$

where $z_t \sim iid$ with mean 0 and unit variance. If h_t can be expressed as:

$$h_t = \omega + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_i \epsilon_{t-i}^2 + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j h_{t-j}, \quad (8)$$

we say that it follows a GARCH(p, q) process (see: Bollerslev (1986) for details).

Apart from the base GARCH(1,1) model, many extensions have been proposed in the literature. In our study, we chose from the following specifications: IGARCH (Engle and Bollerslev, 1986), APARCH (Ding, Granger and Engle, 1993), EGARCH (Nelson, 1991), gjrGARCH (Glosten, Jagannathan and Runkle, 1993). The best model has been chosen based on the properties of residuals and information criteria.

Eventually, in the paper, apart from the plain vanilla GARCH, we used two models that account for the so-called asymmetrical reaction of volatility to good and bad news: APARCH and EGARCH.

The APARCH model (Ding et al., 1993) is parametrized in the following way:

$$h_t^{\delta/2} = \omega + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_i (|\epsilon_{t-i}| - \gamma_i \epsilon_{t-i})^\delta + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j h_{t-j}^{\delta/2}, \quad (9)$$

where γ is an asymmetry parameter. The model is more flexible, since depending on the estimated value of δ we can model different types of non-linear dependencies, other than the conditional variance.

The EGARCH model (Nelson, 1991) is based upon the logarithmic expression of conditional variance:

$$\log h_t = \omega + \sum_{i=1}^q (\alpha_i z_{t-i} + \gamma_i (|z_{t-i}| - E(|z_{t-i}|))) + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j \log h_{t-j}, \quad (10)$$

where α captures the sign effect, and γ represents the size effect.

4.3. Multivariate GARCH models

In this study, we used the bivariate DCC-GARCH model (Engle, 2002). Let us denote by $\epsilon_t = (\epsilon_{1,t}, \epsilon_{2,t})'$ a two-dimensional vector. The DCC model assumes:

$$\epsilon_t | \Omega_{t-1} \sim N(0, H_t), H_t = D_t R_t D_t, \quad (11)$$

where $D_t = \text{diag}(\sqrt{h_{11,t}}, \sqrt{h_{22,t}})$ and conditional variance $h_{ii,t}$ is modelled using the GARCH-type models. In turn, the conditional correlation matrix R_t is given by

$$R_t = (\text{diag}(Q_t))^{-1/2} Q_t (\text{diag}(Q_t))^{-1/2}, \quad (12)$$

with

$$Q_t = (1 - a - b)Q^* + a z_{t-1} z_{t-1}' + b Q_{t-1}, \quad (13)$$

where Q^* is unconditional covariance matrix of z_t ($z_{i,t} = \epsilon_{i,t} / \sqrt{h_{ii,t}}$); a, b are parameters such that $a, b \geq 0$ and $a + b < 1$.

Table 2
Mean of conditional correlation coefficient.

	F.Index	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
CAC 40	0.9892	0.2838	0.3001	-0.0484	0.3130	0.1519
DAX	0.9842	0.3034	0.3168	-0.0538	0.2690	0.1731
FTSE 100	0.9720	0.2920	0.2906	-0.0448	0.3899	0.1539
S&P 500	0.9816	0.3609	0.3567	0.0242	0.2611	0.0784
Nikkei 225	0.9660	0.1474	0.1768	-0.0386	0.1276	0.1929
Hang Seng	0.9749	0.0798	0.1063	-0.0228	0.2070	0.0902

Note: F.Index stands for F.CAC 40, F.DAX, F.FTSE 100, F.S&P 500, F.Nikkei 225, and F.Hang Seng, respectively.

5. Results

Correlation between assets is the critical factor of hedging effectiveness. Table 2 shows the average conditional correlation coefficient estimated from DCC, and in Table 5 in the Appendix, we present the summary statistics. As expected, we obtained the highest correlation for index futures contracts. They are almost perfectly correlated with the stock indices. The correlation between index returns and other instruments is much weaker. We report the same level of dependence around 30% (except for Asian indices) for BTC, ETH and Brent futures. The correlation between gold and indices is roughly twice as weak as that for the latter. Tether (USDT) shows even a negative correlation with stock indices. It meets the definition of a hedging instrument by Baur and Lucey (2010) but will not be able to reduce the risk of stocks significantly for a short position.

We can notice the dependence between assets for alternative market regimes by analysis of Fig. 1, which represents the evolution of the daily dynamic correlations between returns of S&P 500 and hedge candidates. The correlation between S&P 500 returns and each index futures and Tether is usually very stable. However, the first one is close to one (as required by the classical definition of a hedging instrument), and the latter is close to zero (as required by the definition of (Baur and Lucey, 2010)). Note that rapid declines in correlation are the effect of expiring futures contracts and replacing them with another series, but not the divergence between futures and index. Much more volatile is the correlation between the index and other assets. We observe the most negative correlation for gold. Its values fall below -0.25 in three periods. Moreover, it was negative in the first quarter of 2020, when stock markets suffered from the first hit of the COVID-19 pandemic. The finding supports the results of (e.g. Akhtaruzzaman et al. (2021), Ji, Zhang and Zhao (2020) or Kliber (2022)) indicating gold as a safe-haven asset for stock markets in this market crash.

Table 3 presents the results of hedge ratios and in Table 6 in the Appendix, we present the summary statistics. A positive hedge ratio represents a short position of the hedging instrument, whereas a negative one represents a long position. The average values of the hedge ratios are positive, arising from a mostly positive correlation between stock indices and hedging assets (except for Tether for CAC 40, DAX, FTSE 100, Nikkei 225, and Hang Seng). The optimal hedge is formed by taking long and short positions for both assets. For example, a \$100 long position in American stocks should be hedged by taking a short position for \$11.29 in Bitcoin, \$8.76 in Ether, \$57.57 in Tether, \$12.9 in Brent, \$9.61 in gold, and \$98.57 in index futures on average in the optimal hedging. It is clear that a hedge ratio close to zero results in the unprofitability of the hedging strategy since only a minor portion of risk can be reduced through it. In turn, the optimal hedging strategy with Tether for other indices involves this stablecoin in a long trading position.

Fig 2 shows the dynamics of the hedge ratio for S&P 500. For the index futures, the optimal hedge ratio is stable and close to one. Optimal hedging with index futures resembles a full hedge. On the other hand, Tether offers the most volatile hedge ratio. Almost constant correlation and very low volatility of Tether cannot offset the volatility of the stock index in formula 3 and hence the tremendous dynamics of beta. Such a tricky result would disable the hedging strategy's implementation, which forces the portfolio's rebalancing each day. The hedge ratio for gold behaves differently than others in periods of negative correlation. In those periods, the optimal hedging strategy involves gold in a long position to decrease the risk of the base investment. The results obtained for gold bring us to the definition of a hedge or a safe-haven in the spirit of the definition of (Baur and Lucey, 2010).

The final result regarding hedging effectiveness is shown in Table 4 and Table 7 (Appendix) and Figures 3 to 8. The highest *HE* index indicates the highest reduction in variance through hedging. Index futures contracts are very effective hedging tools for each stock market since they enable investors to reduce, on average, at least 93% of variance.

To hedge or not to hedge?

Figure 1: Conditional correlation coefficients between S&P 500 and hedging candidates.

Table 3

Mean of hedge ratio.

	F.Index	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
CAC 40	0.9732	0.0965	0.0779	-1.2812	0.1779	0.2149
DAX	0.9667	0.1060	0.0844	-1.5060	0.1572	0.2531
FTSE 100	0.9811	0.0926	0.0696	-1.0237	0.2090	0.2017
S&P 500	0.9857	0.1129	0.0876	0.5757	0.1290	0.0961
Nikkei 225	0.9439	0.0446	0.0390	-0.9166	0.0662	0.2455
Hang Seng	0.9453	0.0275	0.0275	-0.6505	0.1208	0.1340

Note: F.Index stands for F.CAC 40, F.DAX, F.FTSE 100, F.S&P 500, F.Nikkei 225, and F.Hang Seng, respectively.

Table 4

Mean of hedging effectiveness.

	F.Index	F.Index NH	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
CAC 40	0.9786	0.9591	0.0845	0.0926	0.0023	0.1140	0.0544
DAX	0.9687	0.9578	0.0932	0.1004	0.0029	0.0987	0.0784
FTSE 100	0.9453	0.9226	0.0884	0.0862	0.0020	0.1656	0.0436
S&P 500	0.9670	0.9585	0.1388	0.1460	0.0006	0.0886	0.0276
Nikkei 225	0.9336	0.9247	0.0217	0.0313	0.0015	0.0191	0.0384
Hang Seng	0.9504	0.9445	0.0168	0.0115	0.0005	0.0496	0.0081

Note: F.Index stands for F.CAC 40, F.DAX, F.FTSE 100, F.S&P 500, F.Nikkei 225, and F.Hang Seng, respectively. NH means naïve hedging strategy.

For CAC 40, risk reduction is the highest and exceeds 97%; for Nikkei 225, the lowest but still above 93%. Such a result is an effect of almost perfect correlation and guarantees an almost perfect hedge.

Results for the hedging effectiveness of a naïve hedging strategy do not differ significantly from the optimal hedging strategy using index futures. On average, the highest difference in hedging effectiveness is obtained for FTSE 2.27% and the lowest for Hang Seng 0.59%. The finding supports the result of Wang, Wu and Yang (2015), who state that it

To hedge or not to hedge?

Figure 2: Hedge ratio for S&P 500.

Figure 3: Hedge effectiveness for S&P 500.

Note: NH means naïve hedging strategy. For clarity, the minimum value of HE was trimmed to (-0.5).

is difficult to find a minimum variance strategy that outperforms the simple naïve strategy. The naïve strategy is free of model misspecification and estimation errors. Moreover, when transaction costs are considered, the strategies with time-varying hedge ratios, which frequently require rebalancing hedging positions, may appear even worse. In this paper, we try to determine if another hedging instrument could be a competitor to a futures contract with the index as an underlying asset. Bitcoin and Ether produce very similar hedging effectiveness levels, but the risk reduction only for S&P 500 distinctly exceeds 10%. Brent oil produces a bit higher effectiveness for CAC 40 (11.40%) and FTSE 100

(16.56%), but we cannot indicate the winner between Bitcoin, Ether and oil. Generally, they fail to act as a hedging instrument. Results for gold are even weaker since, on average, a maximum of 7.84% of variance obtained for DAX can be reduced throughout the optimal hedging with gold. The effectiveness of hedging with Tether is very close to zero, indicating that the latter cannot be involved in a hedging strategy for stock markets.

Figures 3 to 8 show the dynamics of hedging effectiveness for considered stock markets. The evolution of HE confirms general findings obtained for average values. Definitely, the best hedging instruments are index futures contracts. The episodes of very low effectiveness that occurred for S&P 500 (Fig. 3) are caused by the way the time series are connected in the triple witching day. For most periods, optimal hedging with index futures seems constant and offers an almost perfect hedge. The results emphasize the reliability of index futures contracts in the hedging role. Other instruments are much worse hedging assets. Brent oil futures mostly outperform other hedging instruments (except for index futures). This feature is the most evident for the FTSE 100 (Fig. 6); however, peaks of the indicator hardly reach 30%. It is worth mentioning that Bitcoin and Ether offer effectiveness for S&P 500 in 2022, oscillating in the interval from 20 to 40% (Fig. 3). This result indicates a relatively substantial portion of risk reduced with cryptocurrencies on the one hand side. However, on the other hand, the level is still much below that obtained for index futures. The effectiveness of gold futures is not high and barely exceeds 20% for European stock markets in the second half of 2022.

6. Conclusions and policy implications

This article aims to evaluate an optimal hedging strategy for several stock markets. As a hedging strategy, we understand a pair-wise portfolio consisting of a long position in stocks (base investment) and a short position in a hedging instrument, put together to minimise the portfolio variance. Given the intensive discussion in the literature on gold, Brent oil, Bitcoin, Ether and Tether as feasible hedging tools, we compare the hedging effectiveness obtained for these instruments with index futures contracts. We find several results that shed new light on the benefits of hedging and thus provide findings relevant for individual and institutional investors.

Regardless of the stock market, the best hedging strategy concerning variance minimisation is based on index futures. Futures offer an almost perfect hedge and thus can reduce the entire risk of benchmark investments. Moreover, they can be used in advanced optimisation-based strategy and naïve hedging strategy, which does not require any computational skills from investors or portfolio rebalancing. Such a strategy is always appropriate for risk-averse investors. When investor attitude to risk differs, and optimal hedging strategy can no longer be accepted, a partial hedging strategy may be implemented. Such an approach gives the investor a flexible tool for risk management tailored to individual needs according to his or her return-risk profile. Moreover, index futures are financial instruments with extremely high liquidity in all stock exchanges. Their ease of access is a serious argument for their implementation in risk management strategies.

The effectiveness of other hedging instruments is much lower compared to almost perfect hedging obtained for index futures. Significant effectiveness (20-40%) was offered by cryptocurrencies Bitcoin and Ether for S&P 500 in 2022. However, they produce volatile effectiveness which requires regular rebalancing to maintain the optimal hedge resulting in increased cost of hedging. Oil futures outperforms other hedging assets (except for index futures) for most of the time and it is the most convincing for FTSE 100. However, hedging with oil produces effectiveness at the level much below that obtained for the index futures. The key question we tried to address was: do these instruments deserve as much attention in the hedging role, given the widespread availability of futures contracts? The answer is negative relative to all assets. Investors have no motivation to implement cryptocurrencies, gold or oil in their hedging strategy. Shorting them to hedge a long position in stocks will always be dominated by strategy using index futures in terms of hedging effectiveness. The usefulness of these instruments may be confirmed in diversification, hedging or safe-haven portfolios consisting of long trading positions, which is not, however, a subject of this work.

A. Appendix

In Table 5 we present the summary statistics of the conditional correlation coefficients, in Table 6 – hedge ratio, while in Table 7 – hedging effectiveness. Figures 4 to 8 display hedging effectiveness of the analysed instruments against CAC 40, DAX, FTSE 100, Nikkei 225 and Hang Seng.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Krzysztof Echaust: Conceptualization of this study, Methodology, Software, Writing - Original draft preparation.
Małgorzata Just: Conceptualization of this study, Methodology, Data Curation, Software, Writing - Original draft preparation.
Agata Kliber: Conceptualization of this study, Methodology, Software, Writing - Original draft preparation.

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Table 5
Summary statistics of conditional correlation coefficient.

Panel A: CAC 40						
	F.CAC 40	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.7850	-0.1112	0.0426	-0.0484	-0.3355	-0.4147
Q1	0.9894	0.2597	0.2785	-0.0484	0.2623	0.0750
Q2	0.9908	0.2844	0.3009	-0.0484	0.3184	0.1701
Q3	0.9925	0.3075	0.3219	-0.0484	0.3810	0.2724
Max	0.9985	0.7684	0.6925	-0.0484	0.6890	0.5339
Panel B: DAX						
	F.DAX	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.8775	0.1330	0.3168	-0.0538	-0.4132	-0.4929
Q1	0.9833	0.2880	0.3168	-0.0538	0.1946	0.0602
Q2	0.9849	0.3030	0.3168	-0.0538	0.2878	0.1939
Q3	0.9872	0.3166	0.3168	-0.0538	0.3713	0.3204
Max	0.9967	0.6438	0.3168	-0.0538	0.6710	0.6567
Panel C: FTSE 100						
	F.FTSE 100	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.5643	0.1807	0.1994	-0.0448	-0.1613	-0.2596
Q1	0.9704	0.2529	0.2585	-0.0448	0.3437	0.0866
Q2	0.9735	0.2860	0.2904	-0.0448	0.3936	0.1570
Q3	0.9775	0.3322	0.3202	-0.0448	0.4557	0.2280
Max	0.9945	0.4746	0.4118	-0.0448	0.7260	0.4995
Panel D: S&P 500						
	F.S&P 500	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.0051	0.1735	-0.1478	-0.0224	-0.1645	-0.3074
Q1	0.9868	0.2865	0.2622	0.0236	0.1674	-0.0229
Q2	0.9919	0.3505	0.3709	0.0246	0.2604	0.0785
Q3	0.9946	0.4339	0.4589	0.0255	0.3541	0.1836
Max	0.9994	0.5741	0.6391	0.0360	0.6699	0.4103
Panel E: Nikkei 225						
	F.Nikkei 225	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.8621	0.1474	0.1768	-0.0386	-0.0738	0.0886
Q1	0.9574	0.1474	0.1768	-0.0386	0.0981	0.1729
Q2	0.9711	0.1474	0.1768	-0.0386	0.1332	0.1920
Q3	0.9807	0.1474	0.1768	-0.0386	0.1610	0.2104
Max	0.9930	0.1474	0.1768	-0.0386	0.3021	0.3254
Panel F: Hang Seng						
	F.Hang Seng	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.9274	-0.4560	0.0508	-0.0228	-0.2204	0.0902
Q1	0.9731	0.0348	0.1004	-0.0228	0.1637	0.0902
Q2	0.9758	0.0796	0.1055	-0.0228	0.2095	0.0902
Q3	0.9782	0.1166	0.1113	-0.0228	0.2501	0.0902
Max	0.9886	0.6134	0.2024	-0.0228	0.6203	0.0902

Table 6
Summary statistics of hedge ratio.

Panel A: CAC 40						
	F.CAC 40	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.5140	-0.0188	0.0051	-5.0015	-0.2463	-1.1837
Q1	0.9240	0.0638	0.0505	-1.9438	0.1184	0.0701
Q2	0.9786	0.0903	0.0704	-0.9222	0.1846	0.2007
Q3	1.0348	0.1212	0.0993	-0.4292	0.2341	0.4067
Max	1.2274	0.3041	0.2433	-0.0565	0.4952	1.1642
Panel B: DAX						
	F.DAX	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.7494	0.0287	0.0201	-6.3621	-0.3565	-1.6256
Q1	0.9005	0.0700	0.0569	-2.3247	0.0930	0.0606
Q2	0.9657	0.1013	0.0777	-1.0970	0.1668	0.2521
Q3	1.0310	0.1303	0.1042	-0.4461	0.2303	0.4887
Max	1.2127	0.2971	0.2373	-0.0629	0.4505	1.4049
Panel C: FTSE 100						
	F.FTSE 100	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.6016	0.0256	0.0184	-3.5383	-0.0775	-0.5258
Q1	0.8789	0.0606	0.0470	-1.5238	0.1538	0.0960
Q2	0.9699	0.0832	0.0623	-0.8487	0.2136	0.1876
Q3	1.0598	0.1122	0.0856	-0.4005	0.2691	0.2892
Max	2.2719	0.2948	0.2144	-0.0564	0.4258	0.9669
Panel D: S&P 500						
	F.S&P 500	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.0036	0.0204	-0.0101	-0.0509	-0.0574	-0.5074
Q1	0.9646	0.0566	0.0397	0.1878	0.0662	-0.0223
Q2	0.9961	0.1040	0.0776	0.3988	0.1190	0.0836
Q3	1.0206	0.1552	0.1285	0.9069	0.1745	0.1876
Max	1.1606	0.3434	0.2809	2.2381	0.4407	0.9036
Panel E: Nikkei 225						
	F.Nikkei 225	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.6630	0.0287	0.0135	-2.7099	-0.0512	0.0599
Q1	0.9142	0.0361	0.0319	-1.4754	0.0437	0.1964
Q2	0.9519	0.0421	0.0374	-0.7932	0.0636	0.2397
Q3	0.9837	0.0497	0.0453	-0.3510	0.0865	0.2922
Max	1.0938	0.1333	0.0838	-0.0368	0.1819	0.7042
Panel F: Hang Seng						
	F.Hang Seng	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.7791	-0.1609	0.0064	-2.1342	-0.1189	0.0524
Q1	0.9164	0.0112	0.0221	-1.0447	0.0849	0.1103
Q2	0.9423	0.0267	0.0265	-0.5125	0.1159	0.1329
Q3	0.9776	0.0400	0.0312	-0.2111	0.1524	0.1524
Max	1.0865	0.1984	0.0712	-0.0138	0.4740	0.2612

Table 7

Summary statistics of hedging effectiveness.

Panel A: CAC 40							
	F.CAC 40	F.CAC 40 NH	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.6162	0.1003	0.0000	0.0018	0.0023	0.0000	0.0000
Q1	0.9788	0.9691	0.0674	0.0776	0.0023	0.0694	0.0124
Q2	0.9818	0.9781	0.0809	0.0905	0.0023	0.1018	0.0347
Q3	0.9850	0.9824	0.0946	0.1036	0.0023	0.1452	0.0788
Max	0.9971	0.9960	0.5905	0.4795	0.0023	0.4748	0.2850
Panel B: DAX							
	F.DAX	F.DAX NH	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.7700	0.7600	0.0177	0.1004	0.0029	0.0000	0.0000
Q1	0.9668	0.9529	0.0830	0.1004	0.0029	0.0436	0.0161
Q2	0.9701	0.9648	0.0918	0.1004	0.0029	0.0844	0.0483
Q3	0.9745	0.9702	0.1003	0.1004	0.0029	0.1379	0.1175
Max	0.9934	0.9900	0.4145	0.1004	0.0029	0.4502	0.4312
Panel C: FTSE 100							
	F.FTSE 100	F.FTSE 100 NH	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.3184	0.1788	0.0327	0.0398	0.0020	0.0001	0.0000
Q1	0.9417	0.9161	0.0640	0.0668	0.0020	0.1182	0.0110
Q2	0.9477	0.9384	0.0818	0.0843	0.0020	0.1549	0.0272
Q3	0.9555	0.9492	0.1104	0.1025	0.0020	0.2076	0.0542
Max	0.9891	0.9887	0.2252	0.1696	0.0020	0.5271	0.2495
Panel D: S&P 500							
	F.S&P 500	F.S&P 500 NE	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.0000	-2.0347	0.0301	0.0005	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Q1	0.9738	0.9716	0.0821	0.0688	0.0006	0.0280	0.0028
Q2	0.9839	0.9827	0.1228	0.1375	0.0006	0.0678	0.0143
Q3	0.9891	0.9881	0.1882	0.2106	0.0007	0.1254	0.0423
Max	0.9987	0.9981	0.3296	0.4085	0.0013	0.4488	0.1683
Panel E: Nikkei 225							
	F.Nikkei 225	F.Nikkei 225 NH	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.7433	0.6935	0.0217	0.0313	0.0015	0.0000	0.0078
Q1	0.9166	0.9083	0.0217	0.0313	0.0015	0.0096	0.0299
Q2	0.9430	0.9373	0.0217	0.0313	0.0015	0.0177	0.0369
Q3	0.9618	0.9578	0.0217	0.0313	0.0015	0.0259	0.0443
Max	0.9861	0.9848	0.0217	0.0313	0.0015	0.0913	0.1059
Panel F: Hang Seng							
	F.Hang Seng	F.Hang Seng NH	BTC	ETH	USDT	F.Brent	F.Gold
Min	0.8601	0.8382	0.0000	0.0026	0.0005	0.0000	0.0081
Q1	0.9470	0.9405	0.0025	0.0101	0.0005	0.0270	0.0081
Q2	0.9522	0.9486	0.0067	0.0111	0.0005	0.0441	0.0081
Q3	0.9568	0.9531	0.0153	0.0124	0.0005	0.0625	0.0081
Max	0.9773	0.9760	0.3762	0.0409	0.0005	0.3848	0.0081

Note: NH means naïve hedging strategy.

To hedge or not to hedge?

Figure 4: Hedge effectiveness for CAC.

Note: NH means naïve hedging strategy.

Figure 5: Hedge effectiveness for DAX.

Note: NH means naïve hedging strategy.

To hedge or not to hedge?

Figure 6: Hedge effectiveness for FTSE 100.

Note: NH means naïve hedging strategy.

Figure 7: Hedge effectiveness for Nikkei 225.

Note: NH means naïve hedging strategy.

To hedge or not to hedge?

Figure 8: Hedge effectiveness for Hang Seng.

Note: NH means naïve hedging strategy.